

holding a rice hill with symptoms similar to those of rice dwarf disease described in Japan: 1) stunting of plants, 2) profuse tillering, and 3) appearance of yellowish white specks forming

interrupted streaks on leaf blades. The streaks are parallel to the midribs.

I recall having told Bill that the symptoms were similar to those of rice dwarf disease but that we needed

transmission results, virus properties, etc. to make that conclusion. Therefore, the information was not published. □

Effect of transplanting time on the spread of tungro in boro

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An experiment at the plant virus experimental field studied the effect of transplanting time on the spread of tungro virus disease in rice during the 1977–78 boro. The Indian Council of

Agricultural Research, New Delhi, funded the research

TN1 seedlings at 25 days of age were transplanted at 5-day intervals in replicated plots, 3 m² each. Each plot was provided with uniform inoculum for tungro virus (1 infected plant/plot). The number of plants with tungro symptoms at the booting stage was recorded.

Transplanting time appears to have pronounced effects on the spread of

tungro (see table). The disease spread among seedlings that were transplanted in December, but not among those transplanted in January. The percentage of infection was high in seedlings transplanted in mid-December, then gradually declined toward the end of the month. Thus, early transplanting in boro may encourage tungro, maybe because tungro vectors are present in the field only until late December and are absent during January. □

Effect of transplanting time of TN1 seedlings on the spread of rice tungro virus disease during the boro season (Dec.–Mar.) and the corresponding vector population in the field. West Bengal, India.

Transplanting date	Vector population/sweep ^a												Plants infected with tungro (%)
	20 Dec 1977	25 Dec	2 Jan 1978	9 Jan	15 Jan	22 Jan	29 Jan	7 Feb	15 Feb	30 Feb	7 Mar	16 Mar	
15 Dec 1977	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	3	80
20 Dec	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	60
25 Dec		2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	30
30 Dec			1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	5
4 Jan 1978				0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
9 Jan				0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0
14 Jan					0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0

^a3-m² plots.

Effects of foliar spray of micronutrients on rice sheath blight disease

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Plants of the susceptible rice variety ADT31 at the maximum-tillering stage were inoculated with the *Rhizoctonia solani* pathogen, which causes sheath blight disease. The field trial had a randomized block design with four replications during the 1975 kuruvai (June–Sept.) and the 1975–76 thaladi (Oct.–Jan.). Two foliar sprays of the micronutrients borax, ammonium molybdate, zinc sulfate, magnesium sulfate, calcium sulfate, copper sulfate,

and ferrous sulfate were applied twice at 0.059% level at 10-day intervals.

Disease intensity was then assessed. All the micronutrients reduced the disease and increased the grain yield in both seasons. The effects were malked with borax, zinc sulfate, copper sulfate, and ferrous sulfate. □

Effects of fungicidal spray on the population of *R. solani* and on rhizospheric microflora of rice

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ADT31, which is susceptible to the sheath blight disease caused by

Rhizoctonia solani, was raised in pots and inoculated with the pathogen. The seedlings were sprayed with a 0.025% solution of the fungicides Brassicol, wetttable cerasan, Thiabendazole, Benlate, Vitavax, Bavistin, Kitazin, Demosan, Daconil, and Hinosan at 20, 25, and 30 days after sowing. The populations of fungi, bacteria, actinomycetes, and *R. solani* in rhizospheric and nonrhizospheric soils were estimated 48 hours later. Fungicidal spray drastically reduced the rhizospheric population of *R. solani*. Foliar sprays of Kitazin, Hinosan, Benlate, Vitavax, and Bavistin reduced the pathogen in the rhizosphere more than the other fungicides did. The fungicidal sprays stimulated the bacterial and actinomycetal populations considerably, but inhibited the fungal populations.